

1 The VDR controls expression of IBD-related genes in a latitude-dependent fashion.

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7 We hypothesized the vitamin D receptor controlled an axis balancing toleragenic needs with
8 pro-inflammatory function in the gastrointestinal (GI) tract immune system. The axis was likely to contain
9 AHR; thus, we proposed control of AHR by the vitamin D receptor. We demonstrate here using cell culture
10 systems and next generation RNA-sequencing control of an organized network of IBD-related genes by
11 the vitamin D receptor, or *VDR*. Studies in cell culture with UV-inducible gene expression together
12 demonstrated latitude-dependent control of the VDR-regulated IBD gene network resulting from
13 sunlight-induced vitamin D expression (sunlight-induced VDR modulation), a discrete latitude-dependent
14 function of exposure to sunlight. The aryl hydrocarbon receptor was a central component of the
15 VDR-regulated IBD network.

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